

Schiff base complexes of some metal ions with vanillin and amino acids

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Abstract : Equilibrium studies on the Schiff base complex systems, viz. Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} -vanillin(van)(A)-l-valine(val)/l-glutamine(gln)/l-glutamic acid(glu)/l-histidine(his)(B) demonstrate the presence of MAB, MA_2B or MA_2B_2 complexes. The stability constant values in the M^{II} -van-val/gln/glu systems indicate that the Schiff base ligand (AB) is tridentate in its $\text{M}(\text{AB})$ complexes, while it is tetradentate in the M^{II} -van-his systems. The results show that the MA_2B and MA_2B_2 complexes can best be represented respectively as $\text{M}(\text{AB})\text{A}$ and $\text{M}(\text{AB})_2$.

Keywords : Schiff base complexes, amino acids, vanillin, metal ions.

Metal complexes of Schiff bases derived from substituted salicylaldehyde and amino acids are non-enzymatic models for many biological systems^{1,2}. Also, transition metal complexes of Schiff bases play an important role in the catalysis of drug interactions³. These findings and their potential applications in many fields such as oxidation catalysts⁴, electro chemistry⁵ etc., stimulated our interest in the investigation of the chemistry of metal-Schiff base complexes. In the present paper, the solution equilibria involved in the Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} -vanillin(van)(A)-L-valine(val), L-glutamine(gln), L-glutamic acid(glu) and L-histidine(his)(B) systems are reported at 25 °C and 0.1 M KNO_3 ionic strength by batch wise titration method⁶⁻⁸.

Results and discussion

In addition to the various binary species HA, MA, MA_2 , HB, H_2B , MB, MB_2 and MB_3 ternary complexes of stoichiometry MAB, MAB_2 and MA_2B_2 have been detected in the Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Zn^{II} -van(A)-val, gln, glu and his(B) systems. MAB and MAB_2 species have been detected in the Cu^{II} -van(A)-val, gln and glu(B) systems, while only MAB species has been found to be present in the Cu^{II} -van(A)-his(B) system (Table 1).

Stability and structure of MAB complexes : The preferential formation of the ternary complex species over binary species can be illustrated by considering the stepwise formation constants of the various species formed, for e.g. in the Co^{II} -van(A)-val(B) system the Scheme 1 clearly indicates the preferential formation of the ternary species over that of the binary complexes.

The $\log \beta_{\text{MAB}}$ values computed in all the systems are higher than the theoretically expected values, where $\log \beta_{\text{MAB}}$ values

Scheme 1

were calculated by considering MAB species to be a simple mixed ligand complex. The higher experimental values indicate the presence of strong inter-ligand interaction between the CHO group of van(A) and the amino group of the amino acid ligand(B). The inter-ligand interaction leads to the formation of a tridentate Schiff base ligand (AB) binding the metal ion through the imino nitrogen, phenolic and carboxylato oxygen atoms in the M^{II} -van-val/gln/glu systems. The $\log \beta$ values for the MAB species in M^{II} -van-gln/glu systems are comparable to that in M^{II} -van-val systems. This suggests same type of binding in the $\text{M}(\text{AB})$ species in the M^{II} -van-gln/glu and M^{II} -van-val systems. In the M^{II} -van-glu systems van and glu ligands bind the metal ion via phenolic oxygen, imino nitrogen and α -carboxylato oxygen atoms. Again, the difference between $\log \beta_{\text{MAB}}$ values in the M^{II} -van-val and M^{II} -van-gln systems indicate that intermolecular association found in the M^{II} -van-gln system is very weak. In the M^{II} -van-his systems the $\log \beta_{\text{MAB}}$ values are ~ 2.5 units higher than that in the corresponding M^{II} -van-val systems, where the Schiff base is tridentate. This shows that in the M^{II} -van-his systems the Schiff base is tetradentate, binding through imidazole,

Table 1. Stability constants for the ternary Schiff base complexes in M^{II}-van(A)-val, gln, glu and his(B) systemsTemp. = 25 °C and I = 0.15 mol dm⁻³ (KNO₃)

Parameter	Co ^{II}				Ni ^{II}				Cu ^{II}				Zn ^{II}			
	val	gln	glu	his	val	gln	glu	his	val	gln	glu	his	val	gln	glu	his
log β _{MAB}	9.10 (6.90)	9.20 (6.95)	8.90 (7.25)	13.30 (9.85)	10.26 (7.70)	10.27 (7.90)	9.98 (8.54)	15.21 (10.81)	14.95 (11.25)	15.00 (11.16)	14.50 (11.71)	19.89 (12.76)	8.98 (7.49)	9.00 (5.47)	8.63 (6.12)	12.48 (8.19)
log β _{MAB₂}	11.11	11.45	10.73	19.18	12.46	12.59	11.78	20.10	19.46	19.97	19.60	–	10.81	10.93	10.24	18.88
log β _{MA₂B₂}	14.10	14.38	13.78	22.12	16.40	16.49	15.88	23.38	–	–	–	–	13.90	13.98	14.34	21.94
Δ log K _{MAB}	1.66	1.76	0.54	3.38	1.76	1.89	0.64	3.40	2.61	2.74	1.50	5.66	1.49	1.61	0.79	3.18

imino nitrogens, phenolic and carboxylato oxygen atoms. This arrangement would result in the formation of one five, one six and one eight membered chelate rings.

The species distribution diagrams also point to the fact that the formation of ternary Schiff base complex MAB is favoured over the formation of binary species. In the Co^{II} systems the CoAB species is predominantly present in the pH range between 5.5 and 7.0 reaching a maximum of 60% of the total metal ion. The Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} systems also follow the same trend. In the Cu^{II} systems, the CuAB species is predominantly present between pH 4.4 and 5.6 and reaches a maximum of 75%. The stabilization factor (Δ log K) calculated for the MAB species in Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}-van-val, gln, glu and his systems follows the Irving-Williams order of stability.

Stability and structure of MAB₂ complexes : The log β values computed for the MAB₂ complexes in the Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}-van-val, gln and glu systems are much higher than those calculated for simple mixed ligand complexes without inter-ligand interaction. The higher experimental values lead to the conclusion that MAB₂ complexes are Schiff bases of the type M(AB)B. The Schiff base (AB) would be tridentate and the second molecule (B) coordinates the metal ion independently.

The log β values for the MAB₂ species in M^{II}-van-gln/glu systems are comparable to those obtained in M^{II}-van-val systems. This suggests the same type of binding in the M(AB)B species in the M^{II}-van-gln/glu and M^{II}-van-val systems. In the MAB₂ species in Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II}-van(A)-his(B) systems the Schiff base (AB) and the second his(B) can coordinate in tridentate modes or the Schiff base (AB) binds the metal ion in a tetradentate mode and the second his(B) is linked bidentately. Comparison of the log K values for the formation of MAB₂ from MAB and MB₂ from MB clearly demonstrates that in M(AB)B species B coordinates the metal ion bidentately. The M(AB)B species was found to be formed above pH 6.0, accounting a maximum of the 20% of the total metal ion in the form of the species in the 1 : 1 systems, and 35% in the 1 : 2 systems.

Stability and structure of MA₂B₂ complexes : MA₂B₂ species was detected in the Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II}-van-val, gln, glu and his systems. The log β values computed in these systems are higher than the statistically expected values, distinctly pointing to the fact that MA₂B₂ species are bis(Schiff base) complexes of the type M(AB)₂, where both the Schiff base ligands (AB) are bound to the metal ion in a tridentate manner leading to octahedral structure. In the M^{II}-van(A)-his(B) systems, the tetradentate binding of (AB) in M(AB)₂ species is not possible because it would lead to the improbable coordination number of eight to the metal ion. To retain the six coordination of the metal ion, two possible structures can be suggested, (i) one (AB) would be tetradentate, while the second (AB) will be bidentate and (ii) both the Schiff base ligands would be tridentate. Of these, structure (ii) appears to be more reasonable.

In 1 : 1 systems, the formation of M(AB)₂ species was found to commence after pH 6.5, while in the 1 : 2 systems M(AB)₂ is the predominant species between pH 6.2 and 7.5. In the 1 : 1 systems, the maximum concentration of M(AB)₂ species is only 26% whereas in the 1 : 2 systems the species concentration reaches 62% of the total metal ion.

Experimental

AnalaR grade metal nitrates were used. The ligand van (G.R., E. Merck) was purified by distilling twice under reduced pressure. The amino acids (Puriss, Fluka) were used as such. In the ternary Schiff base complex systems the equilibrium was attained slowly and hence a batch wise titration procedure was adopted⁶⁻⁸. Calculations were carried out with the help of a computer program⁹ designed for evaluation of Schiff base complex equilibria. The auxiliary data for the binary complexes¹⁰ used under the present experimental conditions were fixed as non-refinable parameters during the computation of Schiff base complex equilibria. The details of the equipment used for the pH titration have been described earlier¹¹. All the experiments were carried out at 25 °C and ionic strength of 0.1 mol dm⁻³ (KNO₃).

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